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Challenges, strengths and weaknesses of different baseline options for monitoring soil carbon removals – insights from the MARVIC project

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For reaching the EU ambition of climate neutrality by 2050, drastic greenhouse gas emission reductions are needed as well as carbon removals. Carbon farming captures CO₂ from the atmosphere and stores carbon in soils and standing vegetation. Land managers get more and more interested as most carbon farming practices deliver also soil based co-benefits such as resilience against weather extremes and positive impacts on biodiversity. Through carbon farming schemes, land managers can get rewarded for their positive contribution to societal challenges by issuing carbon certificates. In recent years, carbon farming schemes are rapidly expanding. Through the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), the European Commission wants to set out criteria for high-quality carbon removal certificates (QU.A.L.I.TY criteria) and rules for monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV). MARVIC is a Soil Mission project that supports the CRCF and aims to develop a framework for the design of harmonized, context-specific MRV systems for carbon farming in arable land, grasslands, agroforestry/woody crops and managed peatlands. It is investigated how different building blocks of benchmark sites, sampling schemes, data layers, farm data, remote sensing and modeling can be smartly assembled to develop robust scalable monitoring systems. In addition, different options for the QU.A.L.I.TY criteria are investigated. Here, we focus on different options to calculate baselines. Two broad categories are standardized (regional) baselines or project-specific baselines. In MARVIC we have identified more than 15 different options, depending e.g., if based on soil organic stock measuring/remeasuring or modeling and ex-ante or ex-post calculations of baselines. For baseline calculations based on modeling, hybrid approaches could exist in which some input parameters are determined ex-ante and others would better be re-determined ex-post, e.g. for also capturing weather extremes in the baseline. The pros and cons of baseline options are assessed against a set of criteria such as cost (allocations), data requirements, scalability and risks and opportunities for farmers, in order to facilitate choices to be made at the policy level.

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Key words Carbon removals, baseline, soil monitoring, carbon farming